

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF HEALTHCARE KNOWLEDGE AND THEIR
ABILITY OF MANAGEMENT IN PAKISTAN**¹Dr. Hifza Rasheed, ²Dr Ayesha Iftikhar, ³Dr Mehvish Arshad¹Allied Hospital Faisalabad.**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

Information is considered a very important source; It offers a competitive advantage. However, if the data is properly processed using data management (KM), this becomes a reserve in favor of the organization's ownership. If PF is implemented in the company, it will improve the struggle for structure, presentation and efficiency, and help in the economical use of assets. Due to strong opposition on the world market, various organizations are moving towards adopting KM. Assistance sectors in many developed countries have fallen in love with access to information management, which will improve data collection from existing activities through the efficient use of data pools. Emerging countries have seized the opportunities & benefits of adopting the framework program. Pakistan is one of the emerging countries that tend to adopt KM in the healthcare sector to increase health success. The study did not mention two main stages of analysis. First, KM activators from previous studies were tested. Secondly, MICMAC (Cross Effect Matrix Processing Applied to Classification) and Structured Information Modeling (ISM) techniques were used to demonstrate the relationship among KM triggers and the driving force and confidence of each trigger. The implementation of MICMAC doctrine and method shows that political incentives, data technology (IT), long-term strategic development and organization of efforts under the Framework Program as part of the Framework Program's business strategy facilitate the adoption of the Framework Program. Trends in Pakistan. KM, an expert of known moderators, can facilitate this in practice. Political incentives will serve as a channel for the adoption of the Framework Program as part of the Pakistani trend.

Keywords: Assessment, Healthcare, Knowledge, Ability, Management, Pakistan.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Hifza Rasheed,**

Allied Hospital Faisalabad.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Hifza Rasheed et al, **Assessment Of Healthcare Knowledge And Their Ability Of Management In Pakistan.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Information management (PF) can be the method used by the organization and individuals to search, share, store, receive, personalize and use data that support the success of the organization¹.

Organizations came to the conclusion that their data should be used if they want to survive in a fast and dynamic environment. KM and information creation enable organizations to customize the chop-chop² dynamic business environment. If the company must be economical and efficient in the approach in which it operates, then it is necessary to adopt a metric linear unit³. Currently, data management has attracted the attention of many students and researchers. Linear metric unit, supply chain, engineering, telecommunications, maintenance industry etc. There is a lot of discussion that data transfer is considered a source of supply. Competitive Advantage of Real Estate⁵. Information is considered the institution's largest source. Many researchers know that there are 2 types of data that are understandable and specific. some data includes everything that is easy to pronounce, encode, access and say, and books, articles, guides, databases, etc. represent types. they can be transferred to another type. Data seems to be difficult to achieve a different result because they are not inherited by monitoring and special experience. KM supports incorrect data expression, which completes the data creation process and increases the organization's success. Organizations involved in data creation have more flexibility to increase their success and use indirect information for additional innovation⁸. In developed countries, information management was used in various structures and processes of social control in this sector. The care sector may be KM's deceased father compared to various business sectors; Adopting FP in the healthcare sector limits patients by providing excellent service, learning from patients, learning new and better ways, and providing a lot of work. Orzano et al. He said that at the national level, PF would significantly improve the success of (medical) observation among healthcare providers and would benefit all patients and doctors. Many developed countries are affected by the adoption of PF under this trend to increase your success in trends. Developing countries now.

However, the adoption of the course is slow. Iran, one of the developing countries, has done the most important work on the kilometers covered⁹. The Pakistani government is trying to find strategies to increase the aid sector, so it is considering miles in the aid sector. The aid sector in West Pakistan faces many

problems and challenges. The (WHO) has announced that West Pakistan has a double disease because hepatitis C is infected by 7.6% of the population. and 5.4% can be calculated as drug-resistant. A large part of the population suffers from malaria; This is the 2nd most commonly reported disease and although it is treatable, most of us die. Pakistan is responsible for 92% of deaths due to protozoal infections worldwide. The percentage of people infected with HIV is about 1%, and 77% of people are growing because of non-selective transfusions. Pakistan's mortality rate is very high; In the first year, 500,000 children have acute systemic infections, tuberculosis, hepatitis, goiter, scabies, diarrhea, malaria, dysentery, hepatitis, etc. It is estimated to be. There are several patients with non-communicable diseases, injuries and mental health problems.

Pakistan has the 7th highest polygenic disease (World Health Organization data). Constant population growth causes bloating and a lot of injury. The Asian healthcare industry should affect more than one patient every day, which is why the Patient Department (OPD) is often overcrowded. There is often a delay in management, resources and achievements. Pakistan is considering opening a metric linear unit to divide these issues by a certain amount.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

From May 2018 to April 2019, the Mayo Hospital is located in the environmental medicine department in Lahore. Use the instructional structural model (ISM) and MICMAC technique to analyze metric triggers of linear units. The method of analyzing the use of this system is divided into three stages. The steps are described below. Step 1: A comprehensive literature review was carried out on metric activators of linear units in the healthcare sector. Those who gave these opportunities met through learning peer-reviewed publications. These publications examined many databases for abuse, such as Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, Emerald, Taylor and Francis and Science Direct. The key words used to extend this research are 'knowledge management', 'medical care' and 'facilitators'. A total of seventy articles from over sixty magazines discovered abuse of these keywords. Two steps have been taken to limit even the most relevant documents. First, repetition of articles is reserved. Secondly, abstracts of other documents were analyzed and unnecessary documents were removed. Finally, three articles from thirty magazines and three conferences.

Left. Popular magazines were the magazines considered for this article (number of articles),

Information Management magazine (7 documents), resources (6 documents), Engineering Management magazine (4 documents) and International Management magazine. Science and engineering management (4 documents), Journal of Management Information Systems (3 documents), Application Information Systems (2 documents) and Behavior and Information Technology (3 documents). Step 2: Many articles were examined in the literature review. Fifteen moderators are indicated in some documents and 5 moderators in others. In total, twenty-five activators were included in the literature. An expert panel was selected to classify Pakistani moderators. The selection of experts was made arbitrarily for the purpose of arbitrary sampling. Initially, thirty health care professionals (doctors, administrative staff, nurses) were contacted via email and telephone, and their data is available on hospital websites. The hospital's operational director agreed to attend an event in which two doctors from two main nurses frequently make e-mails and phone calls. Communication was established with 5 teachers using a similar technique, 2 of them responded to a request to participate. Nursing officer with government information. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (NCP), deputy head of the Department of Health, organized direct conferences to ultimately convince to participate. Finally, a panel of eight specialized nursing advisers was created; All experts participating in this study are highly qualified and competent people with at least 11 years of experience in their fields. Step-by-step

research methodology for this study is shown in Figure 1.

3.1 Interpretative structural analysis (ISM):

Root ISM J.N. Structural modeling (SM) created by the received. Warfield (1999). It is an interactive learning method in which a team of consultants sees a direct and indirect relationship between variables. A model is created that shows better relationships and relationships between variables. This model helps to accept the root cause. The philosophical technique is very popular for many reasons, firstly, there are several problems that need to be solved in research. These problems are complex and difficult to know because of the many relationships between variables. Philosophy defines these relationships and relationships with the help of consultants. Secondly, structural equation modeling (SEM) can be a mathematical technique that helps test variables affecting entanglement, but fails if there is a relationship between variables. The philosophical system technique is used here to create the first model of nursing diploma. Third, the philosophical system can be a sticking method of learning that helps create an ambiguous and poorly created system in a well-defined model. Fourth, it is not necessary to consult prior research in order to use the philosophical system, as a result of which the philosophical system generally requires care, education, supply chain, etc. It is used in various areas such as.

The doctrine model is used by various experts to indicate order and the complex relationship between variables and to present variables in model style. The doctrine was used to analyze the way KM was adopted in engineering trade in the Republic of India. Anantamula and Kanungo.

ISM-MICMAC technique, which studies moderators in business organizations for effective implementation KM. Kumar and Sharma used the MICMAC doctrine and technique to identify and examine obstacles to increased healthcare in rural areas in the Republic of India. Karamat et al. Use the ISM-MICMAC technique.

To recognize and analyze obstacles for KM in the care sector in Pakistan. Some well-defined stages of ISM implementation are Kannan et al.

The steps are as follows.

Step 1 KM activists operating in the healthcare sector review of the literature.

Step 2 Choose triggers using the 5 point scale and geometric mean experiment.

Variables with a value less than 3 are discarded. Step 3 Develop an ordered interaction matrix (SSIM) to demonstrate the relationship as a pair between variables

Step 4 Develop an initial accessibility matrix (IRM) by converting SSIM into 1 and 0.

Step 5 Given temporarily, hidden connections appear if A, B, B are related.

C is related, so A and C are also somehow related,

Step 6 A final accessibility matrix (FRM) has been developed to eliminate all transitions,

Step 7 Create a level section; These variables are created by defining different levels,

Step 8 The ISM model is based on part of the top-level model

level 1, the higher the level, the more critical and finally

Step 9 MICMAC analysis is performed. This is done through management and trust.

Table 1. Various barriers to the use of information management in healthcare Pakistani industry. Information management (KM).

Level	Enablers
1	(14) Promotion of e-data, and (17) Hiring KM personnel's
2	(2) Policy incentives
3	(3) Long-term strategic planning
4	(4) Developing a transparent workflow (5) Eliminate distrust, and (8) Developing collaborative learning atmosphere (12) Employee motivation (13) Employee empowerment (16) Training and education (18) Knowledge filtering
5	(9) Align KM efforts with business strategy (10) IT for KM, and
6	(6) Detection of knowledge brokers, and (11) Categorizing information to avoid overflow of information
7	(1) Management commitment (7) Establishing Customer Relationship Management (CRM), and (15) Customer Feedback

3.1.5 ISM model:

After completing the quantitative section, the next step is to create a conical matrix. The taper matrix result shows the level from level 1 to level 7 (according to this test) as shown in table 1 above. The letter is created after creating the cone string. A letter can be a series of nodes that easily show relationships between

them using the arrows. The degree is displayed with ease of alignment, and thus the ratio of the previous to FRM. After creating the letter, the nurse becomes a belief model. Letter nodes are replaced with the trigger definition. Level one triggers are less critical; because the level is rising, it is necessary. The belief model of this article is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Interpretative structural modeling model for people providing information management practices. Pakistan in the healthcare industry.

3.2 MICMAC analysis:

The philosophical model helps understand the relationships between different triggers, and MICMAC (the cross matrix process used for classification) helps understand how biased it is, unlike the trigger. MICMAC analysis is done with the help of the driver and confidence. The drive power is calculated according to FRM by adding all 1 different cylinder lines. The force of movement indicates the pressure on the piston releases. The dependency power is planned by adding 1s to various FRM activation columns. Confidence indicates the amount of activator that is uncomfortable for opposing activators. Changes are planned in a table that calculates the driving force and relationship. While the dependency power is on the coordinate axis, the drive power is schematic on the coordinate axis. The table is divided into four groups. These groups are independent triggers, sub-

triggers, connection triggers, and independent triggers. explained below. the independent supplier is described below.

Stand-alone trigger: shield triggers and stand-alone triggers, these triggers are weak drive and some power. These activators do not have abundant results in alternative activators. These triggers are disconnected and remain weird.

- Dependent triggers: Q2 triggers are subordinate triggers; these activators are weak It still guarantees solid trust. These activators are strongly influenced by alternative activators. Only one If it works on coercion triggers, it will have an additional effect on triggers.

Link triggers: Q3 triggers are link triggers; The driving force and trust of these facilitators are enormous.

These triggers are extremely unstable, any action on the trigger can be the opposite of the method itself.

_ independent triggers: triggers on the shield IV are independent triggers; These triggers have solid driving but poor addictive power. Action on these activators will affect alternative activators that are passionate about these activators. Activators of individual and blocked buttons are key activators because of their proper drive. The MICMAC analysis of facilitators who facilitate the implementation of KM in the Asian

country sector is detailed in Fig. 3 below. Based on the MICMAC analysis in this study, the I quadrant (autonomous) has one activator and seven facilitators. He was placed here because the driving force was eight and the confidence was seven. All opposing triggers were placed in an equivalent sample. Trigger II (slave) triggers are four, 5, 6, 8 and 11. Key triggers are found in Trimester III (Link) and IV (Standalone). Triggers for the third quarter are twelve, 13, 14, 16, 17 and 18, and the fourth quarter is one, 2, 3, 9, 10 and 15.

Fig. 3. Trust of v / s energy transmission with MICMAC analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

KM has gained in importance in recent years, experts believe that real estate is the key to competitive advantage. Many organizations, along with a solidarity organization, are trying to implement PF to improve their aggression. KM introduces improvements to the business method, ensures better coordination with alternative departments and employees, and protects against data loss. Since the health sector can be a comprehensive information area, the health sector generates a lot of data, this information should be kept to the end with the support of PF. The study was conducted to protect the Pakistani health sector against data loss. Pakistan is currently trying to facilitate the implementation of KM in the care sector, create additional functions and provide the highest quality care services. As KM is in its early stages in Pakistan, analysis in this area is low; In this study, we will try to create facilities that will facilitate the implementation of PF in the Pakistani health sector in Pakistan. In this study, the MICMAC doctrine and technique were used to detect activators and interconnections. The results of the study are as follows.

1. Autonomous facilitators: in this study, the quadrant I has a facilitator, this is poor driving and reliable power. This activator has no major effects and is offline and still irritating. seven (customer relationship management organization (CRM)). This facilitator helps support the implementation of the KM in the care sector of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan. However, the presence of 1 autonomous facilitator shows that the counter-facilitators selected in this analysis are greatly facilitated.
2. Dependent Triggers: Triggers in the 2nd quarter have poor transmission, but they have a lot of confidence. In parallel with current work in this quarter, four triggers (Develop a transparent workflow), five activists (Eliminate uncertainty), six activists (identify a data agent), eight moderators (Develop a collaborative atmosphere) and eleven assistants (prevent overflow information).
3. Fasteners: Triggers in the 3rd quarter are strong driving forces and confidence that are considered one of the main triggers. These facilitators

brutally facilitate opposing facilitators. If one of these triggers is used to help, opposing triggers also offer help. According to this study, III moderator fourteen quarters; facilitator 12 (employee motivation), facilitator thirteen (strengthening employee position), facilitator fourteen (electronic data promotion), facilitator 16 (training and education), facilitator 17 (recruitment of KM employees) and 18 triggers (information filtering).

4. Independent Triggers: Triggers in the 4th quarter have a strong journey, but weak addictive power. These are the most activators (key); First, they support the implementation of PF in the healthcare sector in an Asian country.

According to this study, it is half a dozen triggers, facilitator (management participation), many facilitators (political incentives), facilitator three (long-term strategic planning), facilitator nine (KM hard work strategy), activator ten. (IT for KM) and fifteen activators (customer reviews). The doctrinal model shows variables within a hierarchy type, with the most important being the lowest and least effective. In this study, the doctrinal model shows facilitators like the type of data structures used to apply linear metric units in the Asian health sector. According to this research, a facilitator who can facilitate the implementation of linear metric units best known in the Asian care sector is "political incentive" (activator 2). The government of the Asian people plays an important role in the healthcare sector because it is one of the most important medical infrastructures in the world. The aid sector is responsible for federal and state governments, but districts will be charged for the request. Pakistan has launched several national programs, such as the Community Community Specialist Program, to provide basic medical care and community activities. Pakistan means the development of many services, national health policy (reform of the healthcare sector) (2011), medium-term development framework (2015-2019) and the millennium development goals in the field of health in 2015). Over time, Pakistan has also expanded its aid budget. It's time to include KM in the charity industry to increase success. If the policy is compatible with the aid sector, a long-term strategic plan should be developed to improve vocational education and training practice. A long-term strategic project (trigger 3) is mandatory for the implementation of PF. Perera and Peiró stated that strategic design is mandatory for all types of organizations, especially organizations in the aid sector. Thanks to the strategic project, aid sector organizations will achieve their short-, medium- and long-term goals and take action

for a better future. Vision, mission and values should be clearly defined in a semi-permanent strategic project. The Ministry of Health (Pakistan) has completed the importance of a strategic project and developed a Vision of Health for the Nation¹¹. This document clearly shows the vision, mission and values of the care sector and wants to improve health standards in an Asian country. Hospitals without a public sector have good competition from the public sector. NGOs are relatively longer if they have a strategic plan, but they can be significantly improved. each of them will benefit significantly from the implementation of a strategic project for the public sector and general personnel of PF. Public and private healthcare institutions want to introduce linear metric units, such as 13. Therefore, it turns out to be the AN supplier for the metric linear unit. An effective, semi-permanent planned project offers additional opportunities. An effective strategic design ensures that the efforts of the metric linear unit, business strategy (actuator 9) and metric linear unit (actuator 10) are compatible with information technology (IT). There are several strategic plans in giant organizations. To succeed, these plans must be consistent and compatible. Greiner et al. He stated that in order to use the metric linear unit in practice, there should be AN agreement with the business strategy. Similarly, the strategy for implementing the metric linear unit should generally be consistent with the strategy of the Ministry of Health for organizations in the public care sector. The Ministry of Health (Pakistan) is looking for new strategies to increase its success in the care sector; This can convince you that he is an effective CM exercise moderator. Long-term methods of using KM will require technology in hospitals because the mileage depends on kilometers (trigger 10). Acharyulu said it is necessary to focus on one kilometer to successfully address global health problems and future trends¹⁴. Over time, the Ministry of Health increased technology charges to cope with existing changes. Try using additional technology to improve IT and support. In 2019, USD 4.05 billion was spent on the maintenance sector, which is 42.86% compared to the previous year. The amount spent on technology in 2021 is expected to be USD 557.2 million and USD 537.5 million. The private sector is a permanent step in the public sector when it comes to technology. technology is therefore an important factor that facilitates the use of VET in the Asian help sector and offers more opportunities to provide alternative facilities. Adaptation of FP transactions to business strategy (trigger 9) and IT for KM (trigger 10) includes management involvement (trigger 1), CRM configuration (trigger 7) and customer feedback (trigger 15). Administrative support is the key to

implementing any PR strategy or system [22]. Managers should even be concerned about using KM to verify their success in the help industry. This will have a major impact on the implementation of a convincing UN government agency supporting MH [85, 86]. Efforts should be made to inspire management (administration) to participate and implement PR practice in the Public Assistance Sector Organization (Pakistan). Due to the huge organization infrastructure in the public services sector, this will not be easy, but this can be achieved by developing policy indicators. Private care organizations (Pakistan) are more active and interested in their clients and can only ask for KM. Private hospitals are moving towards CRM to increase their success and strengthen their customer base. KM CRM focuses on customer information to ensure the highest quality of customer service¹⁵. In addition to CRM, a customer feedback system (internal or external customer) must be installed, feedback helps the KM method by creating changes in the KM system to create an additional cheap and easy system. The personal sector is fast and requires feedback from customers; They are constantly looking for opportunities to improve their business. Listening to their doctors and various employees of the World Health Organization (internal clients), they also report their complaints or suggestions if they have problems as patients (external clients). The public sector does not listen to CRM; No current full patient feedback system. The introduction of such facilitators can help organizations in the public health sector to effectively implement the EaP. These triggers can cause multiple triggers.

RESULTS:

Business organizations are now turning to managing their data to gain a competitive advantage over their competitors. Organizations that manage their data well will be better in the future. Organizations in the healthcare sector rely heavily on internal and external data and data. External data comes from printed literature and private conferences with doctors. The details come from the knowledge and skills of employees. Combining these two together helps generate new data storage.

Information is required in hospitals for two reasons. First of all, it helps increase success.

patient data, and secondly, some organizations in the care sector U. U. Save data to protect against lawsuits. The Ministry of Health (Pakistan) is trying to find new strategies and ways to improve care services; This study proposes FP as a way to improve healthcare as part of healthcare. Many healthcare providers in

developed countries accept this because it generates the benefits of having KM. Developing countries are trying to use KM to jointly increase their success. Pakistan is trying to apply new techniques to increase the effectiveness of protection. Therefore, in this study, KM as AN can increase success in maintenance, because no analysis is a gift to KM's Pakistani practice in the care sector. The purpose of this study is to identify and analyze discursive relationships between entities that facilitate victimization techniques, and to improve the hierarchy of leaders in the Pakistani health sector. After reviewing the literature and KM indicators by a panel of eight experts, 18 activators were replaced during the study. Driving force and addiction depend on the use of belief technology. The faith model of this research shows facilitators in an extremely important data structure, from the most important to the smallest. Eighteen known moderators in this study are divided into seven levels. According to the results of this study, the main facilitator, political incentive (facilitator 2) and alternative facilitators inspiring structure are to align their efforts with the long-term strategic project (facilitator 3). In the trading strategy, KM (trigger 9) and BT (trigger 10) are also required for KM. These are independent obstacles, they have a solid driving force, but they have little confidence. The Government of Pakistan (Ministry of Health) plays an important role in the healthcare sector; Appropriate principles for implementing FP in Pakistani healthcare should be developed.

REFERENCES:

1. Javed, Saad Ahmed, Sifeng Liu, Amin Mahmoudi, and Muhammad Nawaz. "Patients' satisfaction and public and private sectors' health care service quality in Pakistan: Application of grey decision analysis approaches." *The International journal of health planning and management* 34, no. 1 (2019): e168-e182.
2. Bilal, Hafiz Muhammad, Neelam Iqbal, and Muhammad Kamran Raza. "HYPERTENSION; ASSESSMENT OF RISK FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH HYPERTENSION AND THE KNOWLEDGE OF OUTPATIENTS ABOUT THEIR HEALTH STATUS: A MULTICENTER, CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY IN MULTAN, PAKISTAN." *Professional Medical Journal* 26, no. 1 (2019).
3. Javaeed, Arslaan. "General Needs Assessment of the Undergraduate Medical Students to Integrate Courses on Medical Ethics, Time Management and Communication Skills into the Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery Curriculum of

- Pakistani Medical Colleges." *Cureus* 11, no. 4 (2019).
4. Arslaan, Javaeed. "General Needs Assessment of the Undergraduate Medical Students to Integrate Courses on Medical Ethics, Time Management and Communication Skills into the Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery Curriculum of Pakistani Medical Colleges." *Cureus* 11, no. 4 (2019).
 5. Shaikh, Beenish Tahir, Shehnaz Wasim, Hafsa Yasin, Sidra Khalid, and Malick Muhammed Sabih Masood. "MATERNAL KNOWLEDGE OF WHO GUIDELINES FOR TREATMENT OF ACUTE RESPIRATORY INFECTIONS IN CHILDREN UNDER FIVE IN PAKISTAN." *Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbottabad* 31, no. 4 (2019): 530-535.
 6. Meghani, Shaista, Rozina Karmaliani, Khairunnissa Ajani, Shireen Shehzad Bhamani, Nadeem Ullah Khan, and Nasreen Lalani. "Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Healthcare Professionals Regarding Family Presence During Resuscitation: An Interventional Study in a Tertiary Care Setting, Karachi, Pakistan." *Connect: The World of Critical Care Nursing* 13, no. 1 (2019): 46-55.
 7. Naqvi, Atta Abbas, Mohamed Azmi Hassali, Wajiha Iffat, Madiha Zia, Mustajab Fatima, Sadia Shakeel, Irfanullah Khan et al. "Development and validation of a novel rheumatoid arthritis knowledge assessment scale in Pakistani patients with rheumatoid arthritis." *International journal of rheumatic diseases* 22, no. 11 (2019): 2031-2044.
 8. Maul, Kayleigh M., Rubaba Naeem, Uzma Rahim Khan, Asad I. Mian, Aisha K. Yousafzai, and Nick Brown. "Child abuse in Pakistan: A qualitative study of knowledge, attitudes and practice amongst health professionals." *Child abuse & neglect* 88 (2019): 51-57.
 9. Akram, Saima, Zaeem Arif, Shoaib Khan, and Sanam Tauheed. "Knowledge, awareness and practice of forensic odontology among dental practitioners in Karachi, Pakistan." *The Pakistan Journal of Medicine and Dentistry* 8, no. 1 (2019): 4-4.
 10. Al Khamisi, Yousuf Nasser, M. Khurshid Khan, and J. Eduardo Munive-Hernandez. "Knowledge-based lean Six Sigma system for enhancing quality management performance in healthcare environment." *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma* (2019).
 11. Jawad, Fatima Ali, Sanam Soomro, Saher Aijaz, and Tazeen Saeed Ali. "Knowledge and Practices of Family Planning (FP) Methods among Women Living in Semi-Urban Areas of Karachi, Pakistan." *i-Manager's Journal on Nursing* 9, no. 3 (2019): 18.
 12. Ahmed, Shahbaz, and Sidra Kanwal. "The Mediating Role of Customer Satisfaction between Service Quality and Loyalty Behavior: Assessing the PAKSERV Model in Pakistan Islamic Banking."
 13. Irfan, Babar, Ibrahim Zahid, Muhammad Sharjeel Khan, Omar Abdul Aziz Khan, Shayan Zaidi, Safia Awan, Sobia Bilal, and Omar Irfan. "Current state of knowledge of basic life support in health professionals of the largest city in Pakistan: a cross-sectional study." *BMC health services research* 19, no. 1 (2019): 865.
 14. Hayat, Aamir, Asad Afzal Humayon, Muhammad Kashif Aslam, Muhammad Azeem, Muhammad Nadir Hussain Khan, and Munir Ahmed. "The Relationship between Knowledge Management Practices and Organizational Performance: Evidence from Banking Sector of Southern Punjab, Pakistan." *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences: Proceedings* 8, no. 4 (s) (2019): pp-37.
 15. Abdullah, Muhammad, and Rubeena Zakar. "Health Literacy in South Asia: Clarifying the Connections between Health Literacy and Wellbeing in Pakistan." *Health* 34, no. 2 (2019): 575-589.